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Cytomegalovirus and lung cancer - a causal relationship?

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

The relationship between human cytomegalovirus infection and human lung cancer has been investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

New statistical methods were used.

RESULTS:

Without CMV infection, no smoking of tobacco. Without smoking of tobacco, no human lung cancer. Ergo: Without CMV infection, no human lung cancer.

CONCLUSION:

Within a CMV infection, the cause of human lung cancer will be found.

Keywords:

CMV; Cytomegalovirus; Lung cancer; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

The history ¹ of human cytomegalovirus (CMV) with corresponding back and forth is quite turbulent. Moritz Wilhelm Hugo Ribbert (1855-1920) was the first to document large inclusion-bearing cells in the kidneys of an infant (see Ribbert, 1904). It didn't take long and Goodpasture and Talbot suggest in 1921 that the 'cytomegalia' could be due to a viral agent (see Goodpasture and Talbot, 1921). In 1950, Smith and Vellios showed that a 'cytomegalia' infection may occur even in utero (see Smith and Vellios, 1950). Finally, with considerable effort, Smith (see Smith, 1956) in 1956, Rowe and coworkers (see Wallace et al., 1956) in 1956, and Weller et al (see Weller et al., 1957) in 1957 independently of each other succeeded in isolating human 'cytomegalia' strains. In the end, in 1960, Weller and coworkers (see Weller et al., 1960) coined the term 'cytomegalovirus'. Human cytomegalovirus (CMV) or human herpesvirus-5 ² (HHV-5), is a double-stranded deoxyribonucleic ³ acid (DNA) virus consisting of two unique regions and a member of the viral family known as herpesviruses, Herpesviridae. The highly complex eukaryotic CMV with its intrinsic ability to induce cell enlargement, or cytomegalia, encodes approximately for 200 genes. ⁴ Meanwhile, the complete genetic content of viruses like Epstein-Barr virus ⁵ (EBV), varicella zoster virus ⁶ (VZV), the herpes simplex virus type 1 ⁷ (HSV-1) and of other ⁸ viruses has been determined. In point of fact, scientist succeeded in sequencing ⁹ CMV too. CMV infects between more than 60% of adults ¹⁰ with an increase in the

¹Riley HD Jr. History of the cytomegalovirus. *South Med J.* 1997 Feb;90(2):184-90. doi: 10.1097/00007611-199702000-00004. PMID: 9042169. Format:

²Lefkowitz EJ, Dempsey DM, Hendrickson RC, Orton RJ, Siddell SG, Smith DB. Virus taxonomy: the database of the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV). *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2018 Jan 4;46(D1):D708-D717. doi: 10.1093/nar/gkx932. PMID: 29040670; PMCID: PMC5753373.

³Watson JD, Crick FH. Molecular structure of nucleic acids; a structure for deoxyribose nucleic acid. *Nature.* 1953 Apr 25;171(4356):737-8. doi: 10.1038/171737a0. PMID: 13054692.

⁴Bankier AT, Beck S, Bohni R, Brown CM, Cerny R, Chee MS, Hutchison CA 3rd, Kouzarides T, Martignetti JA, Preddie E, et al. The DNA sequence of the human cytomegalovirus genome. *DNA Seq.* 1991;2(1):1-12. doi: 10.3109/10425179109008433. PMID: 1666311.

⁵Baer R, Bankier AT, Biggin MD, Deininger PL, Farrell PJ, Gibson TJ, Hatfull G, Hudson GS, Satchwell SC, Séguin C, et al. DNA sequence and expression of the B95-8 Epstein-Barr virus genome. *Nature.* 1984 Jul 19-25;310(5974):207-11. doi: 10.1038/310207a0. PMID: 6087149.

⁶Davison AJ, Scott JE. The complete DNA sequence of varicella-zoster virus. *J Gen Virol.* 1986 Sep;67 (Pt 9):1759-816. doi: 10.1099/0022-1317-67-9-1759. PMID: 3018124.

⁷McGeoch DJ, Dalrymple MA, Davison AJ, Dolan A, Frame MC, McNab D, Perry LJ, Scott JE, Taylor P. The complete DNA sequence of the long unique region in the genome of herpes simplex virus type 1. *J Gen Virol.* 1988 Jul;69 (Pt 7):1531-74. doi: 10.1099/0022-1317-69-7-1531. PMID: 2839594.

⁸Johnson GP, Goebel SJ, Perkus ME, Davis SW, Winslow JP, Paoletti E. Vaccinia virus encodes a protein with similarity to glutaredoxins. *Virology.* 1991 Mar;181(1):378-81. doi: 10.1016/0042-6822(91)90508-9. PMID: 1994586.

⁹Chee MS, Bankier AT, Beck S, Bohni R, Brown CM, Cerny R, Horsnell T, Hutchison CA 3rd, Kouzarides T, Martignetti JA, et al. Analysis of the protein-coding content of the sequence of human cytomegalovirus strain AD169. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol.* 1990;154:125-69. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-74980-3_6. PMID: 2161319.

¹⁰Cannon MJ, Schmid DS, Hyde TB. Review of cytomegalovirus seroprevalence and demographic characteristics associated with infection. *Rev Med Virol.* 2010 Jul;20(4):202-13. doi: 10.1002/rmv.655. PMID: 20564615.

population's seroprevalence ¹¹ , ¹² , ¹³ , ¹⁴ with increasing age. ¹⁵ In fact, children 6-11-year-old are 36.3% CMV positive. As known, CMV seroprevalence ¹⁶ is increasing gradually with age and can be found in those aged ≥ 80 years in more than 90.8% of cases. ¹⁷ After recovery of a primary CMV infection, CMV remains dormant within the myeloid cells of the host over long periods with more or less a frequent viral reactivation. Nonetheless, a CMV infection ¹⁸ with clinical manifestations ranging from asymptomatic to life-threatening states makes it difficult to manage this infection effectively with today's very meager (cidofovir, foscarnet, ganciclovir, valganciclovir et cetera) possibilities. ¹⁹ , ²⁰ Meanwhile, it was possible to detect CMV mRNA, CMV DNA, and/or CMV antigens in tumour tissues and to provide seroepidemiologic evidence of CMV infection in the etiology of several human malignancies. ²¹ , ²² Previous studies have provided some evidence of higher anti CMV antibody levels in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). ²³ And much more than this. Nenna et al. were able to determine a strong relationship between CMV serology and the risk of dying from COPD. According to Nenna et al., CMV serology was associated with cancer mortality ²⁴ too. Despite the obvious danger of exposing oneself to public ridicule, theoretically, a possible (causal) relationship between CMV and lung cancer ²⁵ (LC) does not seem completely out of question.

¹¹Staras SA, Dollard SC, Radford KW, Flanders WD, Pass RF, Cannon MJ. Seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus infection in the United States, 1988-1994. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2006 Nov 1;43(9):1143-51. doi: 10.1086/508173. Epub 2006 Oct 2. PMID: 17029132.

¹²Staras SA, Flanders WD, Dollard SC, Pass RF, McGowan JE Jr, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence and childhood sources of infection: A population-based study among pre-adolescents in the United States. *J Clin Virol*. 2008 Nov;43(3):266-71. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2008.07.012. Epub 2008 Sep 7. PMID: 18778968.

¹³Bate SL, Dollard SC, Cannon MJ. Cytomegalovirus seroprevalence in the United States: the national health and nutrition examination surveys, 1988-2004. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2010 Jun 1;50(11):1439-47. doi: 10.1086/652438. PMID: 20426575.

¹⁴Lachmann R, Loenenbach A, Waterboer T, Brenner N, Pawlita M, Michel A, Thamm M, Poethko-Müller C, Wichmann O, Wiese-Posselt M. Cytomegalovirus (CMV) seroprevalence in the adult population of Germany. *PLoS One*. 2018 Jul 25;13(7):e0200267. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0200267. PMID: 30044826; PMCID: PMC6059406.

¹⁵Gupta M, Shorman M. Cytomegalovirus. [Updated 2022 Aug 8]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK459185/>

¹⁶Zuhair M, Smit GSA, Wallis G, Jabbar F, Smith C, Devleeschauwer B, Griffiths P. Estimation of the worldwide seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Rev Med Virol*. 2019 May;29(3):e2034. doi: 10.1002/rmv.2034. Epub 2019 Jan 31. PMID: 30706584.

¹⁷Staras SA, Dollard SC, Radford KW, Flanders WD, Pass RF, Cannon MJ. Seroprevalence of cytomegalovirus infection in the United States, 1988-1994. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2006 Nov 1;43(9):1143-51. doi: 10.1086/508173. Epub 2006 Oct 2. PMID: 17029132.

¹⁸Chen SJ, Wang SC, Chen YC. Antiviral Agents as Therapeutic Strategies Against Cytomegalovirus Infections. *Viruses*. 2019 Dec 23;12(1):21. doi: 10.3390/v12010021. PMID: 31878068; PMCID: PMC7019738.

¹⁹Mozaffar M, Shahidi S, Mansourian M, Badri S. Optimal Use of Ganciclovir and Valganciclovir in Transplanted Patients: How Does It Relate to the Outcome? *J Transplant*. 2018;2018:8414385.

²⁰Bartlett AW, Hall BM, Palasanthiran P, McMullan B, Shand AW, Rawlinson WD. Recognition, treatment, and sequelae of congenital cytomegalovirus in Australia: An observational study. *J Clin Virol*. 2018 Nov;108:121-125. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2018.09.017. Epub 2018 Sep 27. PMID: 30300787.

²¹Michaelis M, Doerr HW, Cinatl J. The story of human cytomegalovirus and cancer: increasing evidence and open questions. *Neoplasia*. 2009 Jan;11(1):1-9. doi: 10.1593/neo.81178. PMID: 19107226; PMCID: PMC2606113.

²²Cinatl J, Scholz M, Kotchetkov R, Vogel JU, Doerr HW. Molecular mechanisms of the modulatory effects of HCMV infection in tumor cell biology. *Trends Mol Med*. 2004 Jan;10(1):19-23. doi: 10.1016/j.molmed.2003.11.002. PMID: 14720582.

²³Tan DB, Amran FS, Teo TH, Price P, Moodley YP. Levels of CMV-reactive antibodies correlate with the induction of CD28(null) T cells and systemic inflammation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). *Cell Mol Immunol*. 2016 Jul;13(4):551-3. doi: 10.1038/cmi.2015.4. Epub 2015 Jan 26. PMID: 27402584; PMCID: PMC4947821.

²⁴Nenna R, Zhai J, Packard SE, Spangenberg A, Sherrill DL, Martinez FD, Halonen M, Guerra S. High cytomegalovirus serology and subsequent COPD-related mortality: a longitudinal study. *ERJ Open Res*. 2020 Apr 27;6(2):00062-2020. doi: 10.1183/23120541.00062-2020. PMID: 32363208; PMCID: PMC7184115.

²⁵Ferlay J, Colombet M, Soerjomataram I, Mathers C, Parkin DM, Piñeros M, Znaor A, Bray F. Estimating the global cancer incidence and mortality in 2018: GLOBOCAN sources and methods. *Int J Cancer*. 2019 Apr 15;144(8):1941-1953. doi: 10.1002/ijc.31937. Epub 2018 Dec 6. PMID: 30350310.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.2. CMV and smoking

Li et al. ²⁶ provided data on the relationship CMV infection and smoking.

2.3. Smoking and lung cancer

Vikas Khurana et al. ²⁷ provided data on the relationship smoking and lung cancer.

2.4. CMV and lung cancer

Theorem 7: $((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t) = +1$ of the publication Single and compound conditions ²⁸, Version 2 has been used to investigate the relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer.

2.5. CMV and lung cancer

Kuo et al. ²⁹ determined CMV viral loads in leukocytes by a real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR), a technique which amplifies specific DNA sequences with remarkable efficiency. ³⁰ Blood samples were collected from each of 15 patients with newly diagnosed malignant disease. Additionally, a responses to changes in viral loads were assessed by assaying tumour necrosis factor (TNF)-alpha and CMV-specific IgG titres and interferon (IFN)-gamma levels. Of the 15 participants, two had lung cancer, while 13 had no lung cancer, 11 had head and neck cancers, one had lymphoma and one had rectal cancer. In toto, 2/2 lung cancer patients were CMV positive, 1/13 non lung cancer patient were CMV negative.

²⁶Li Z, Tang Y, Tang N, Feng Q, Zhong H, Liu YM, Wang LM, He F. High anti-human cytomegalovirus antibody levels are associated with the progression of essential hypertension and target organ damage in Han Chinese population. *PLoS One*. 2017 Aug 24;12(8):e0181440. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0181440. PMID: 28837559; PMCID: PMC5570371.

²⁷Khurana V, Bejjanki HR, Caldito G, Owens MW. Statins reduce the risk of lung cancer in humans: a large case-control study of US veterans. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1282-8. doi: 10.1378/chest.06-0931. PMID: 17494779.

²⁸Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Single and compound conditions. *Causation*, 18(10), 5–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535107>, p. 24.

²⁹Kuo CP, Wu CL, Ho HT, Chen CG, Liu SI, Lu YT. Detection of cytomegalovirus reactivation in cancer patients receiving chemotherapy. *Clin Microbiol Infect*. 2008 Mar;14(3):221-7. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-0691.2007.01895.x. Epub 2007 Dec 5. PMID: 18070129.

³⁰Bell J. The polymerase chain reaction. *Immunol Today*. 1989 Oct;10(10):351-5. doi: 10.1016/0167-5699(89)90193-X. PMID: 2679632.

2.6. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*³¹ too.

2.6.1. Statistical methods

The probability of the exclusion relationship $p(\text{EXCL})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B)$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of an exclusion relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019c). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, left-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided left-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a positive causal relationship would contradict an exclusion relationship and vice versa.

The probability of the necessary condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019c). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship ($k < 0$) would contradict a necessary condition relationship and vice versa.

The probability of the sufficient condition relationship $p(\text{IMP})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b, 2022) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | \underline{B})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of an sufficient condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019c). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been

³¹Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship would contradict a sufficient condition relationship and vice versa.

Many times, potential publication bias among the studies is assessed by Begg's funnel plot³²,³³,³⁴,³⁵ with something like a treatment effect (horizontal axis) and some measure of weight (inverse variance, standard error, sample size et cetera) on the vertical axis. It is not always an easy task to bring various studies together which differ in different aspects in order to re-analyse the same or for doing a meta-analysis. Due to several reasons, variability in the data of the studies and other difference might be found. These days the heterogeneity among the studies is assessed through a so called I^2 statistics³⁶,³⁷,³⁸ to. Under usual circumstances, an I^2 value of 25%, 50% and 75% are regarded as low, moderate and high heterogeneity³⁹. In this investigation, we preferred to control the study (design) bias and the heterogeneity among the studies by IOI, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) and by IOU, the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019b).

All the data were analysed using MS Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA). P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

³²Light RJ, Pillemer DB. Summing up. The science of reviewing research. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1984.

³³Egger M, Davey Smith G, Schneider M, Minder C. Bias in meta-analysis detected by a simple, graphical test. *BMJ*. 1997 Sep 13;315(7109):629-34. doi: 10.1136/bmj.315.7109.629. PMID: 9310563; PMCID: PMC2127453.

³⁴Begg CB, Mazumdar M. Operating characteristics of a rank correlation test for publication bias. *Biometrics*. 1994 Dec;50(4):1088-101. PMID: 7786990.

³⁵Lau J, Ioannidis JP, Terrin N, Schmid CH, Olkin I. The case of the misleading funnel plot. *BMJ*. 2006 Sep 16;333(7568):597-600. doi: 10.1136/bmj.333.7568.597. PMID: 16974018; PMCID: PMC1570006.

³⁶Cochran WG. The combination of estimates from different experiments. *Biometrics* 1954; 10(1): 101-29.

³⁷Higgins JP, Thompson SG. Quantifying heterogeneity in a meta-analysis. *Stat Med*. 2002 Jun 15;21(11):1539-58. doi: 10.1002/sim.1186. PMID: 12111919.

³⁸Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557. PMID: 12958120; PMCID: PMC192859.

³⁹Higgins JP, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-analyses. *BMJ*. 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.327.7414.557. PMID: 12958120; PMCID: PMC192859.

3. Results

3.1. CMV and smoking

Li et al. ⁴⁰ documented a seroprevalence of CMV Immunoglobulin G (IgG) in the Han Chinese population as $(547 / 563) \times 100 = 97.16\%$. How does people cope with such a threat? The underlying question is whether CMV-positive people have learned that smoking of tobacco is of help to cope with such a profound and far-reaching challenge? Li et al. provided data on the relationship between CMV infection and consumption of nicotine. These data were re-analysed.

Table 1. The relationship between CMV IgG and smoking of tobacco (Study of Li et al, 2017).

		Smoking of tobacco		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	192	355	547
	NO	5	11	16
		197	366	563

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship k = 0,01341537
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,48950308
p (SINE) = 0,99111901
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,97461929
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,68750000
P VALUES.
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,48950308
 χ^2 (SINE— Not A_i) = 1,56
 χ^2 (SINE— B_i) = 0,13
 P Value (SINE) = 0,00884168
PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (192 / 547) \times 100 = 35,10 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (355 / 547) \times 100 = 64,90 \%$
 $(c / \text{not } A) \times 100 = (5 / 16) \times 100 = 31,25 \%$
 $(d / \text{not } A) \times 100 = (11 / 16) \times 100 = 68,75 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (192 / 197) \times 100 = 97,46 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (5 / 197) \times 100 = 2,54 \%$
 $(b / \text{not } B) \times 100 = (355 / 366) \times 100 = 96,99 \%$
 $(d / \text{not } B) \times 100 = (11 / 366) \times 100 = 3,01 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (547 / 563) \times 100 = 97,16 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (16 / 563) \times 100 = 2,84 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (197 / 563) \times 100 = 34,99 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (366 / 563) \times 100 = 65,01 \%$
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
 RR (necessary condition) = 1,12321755
 RR (sufficient condition) = 1,00481876
 Relative risk reduction (RRR) = -12,32 %
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
 Odds ratio (OR) = 1,18985915
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,00312735
STUDY DESIGN.
 p(IOU)= 0,32149201
 p(IOI)= 0,62166963

⁴⁰Li Z, Tang Y, Tang N, Feng Q, Zhong H, Liu YM, Wang LM, He F. High anti-human cytomegalovirus antibody levels are associated with the progression of essential hypertension and target organ damage in Han Chinese population. PLoS One. 2017 Aug 24;12(8):e0181440. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0181440. PMID: 28837559; PMCID: PMC5570371.

The prevalence of CMV in the population, estimated on the basis of the control group, is about $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (355 / 366) \times 100 = 96,99\%$ which is not without any relationship to reality. Nonetheless, in order to assure a fair study design and to obtain a $p(\text{IOU})$ as much as possible near or even equal to zero, the size of the control group (Not B) should have been about 20 times greater than it has been, i. e. about 7000 subjects. As a consequence, the relationship between CMV positivity and smoking of tobacco will be probably much stronger than suggested by the data of Li et al. With due caution, we have some slight reason to accept the null hypothesis:

without CMV infection, **no** smoking of tobacco (P value = 0,0088416).

3.2. Smoking and lung cancer

Many so-called risk factors for lung cancer have been identified by time. At the end, smoking is the most prominent modifiable risk factor of lung cancer. However, it is necessary to note very critically that 10 to 15% of lung cancers⁴¹ occur in those who are lifetime never-smokers. Furthermore, none study provided evidence that smoking is a sufficient condition of lung cancer. In a review and meta-analysis of the relationship between smoking and lung cancer $433 / 48393 = 0.008947575063$ or about 9 from 1000 never smoked but suffered still from lung cancer.⁴²

Table 2. The relationship between smoking of tobacco and lung cancer (Study of Khurana et al. 2007).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Smoking of tobacco	YES	3410	176247	179657
	NO	1262	121422	122684
		4672	297669	302341

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = 0,03461136$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 p (SINE) = 0,99582591
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/B)$ > 0,72988014
 p (SINE) approx.= $1-(c/(Not A))$ > 0,98971341

P VALUES.
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_i) = 12,98
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_i) = 340,89
 P Value (SINE) = 0,00416540

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (3410 / 179657) \times 100 = 1,90 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (176247 / 179657) \times 100 = 98,10 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (1262 / 122684) \times 100 = 1,03 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (121422 / 122684) \times 100 = 98,97 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (3410 / 4672) \times 100 = 72,99 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1262 / 4672) \times 100 = 27,01 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (176247 / 297669) \times 100 = 59,21 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (121422 / 297669) \times 100 = 40,79 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (179657 / 302341) \times 100 = 59,42 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (122684 / 302341) \times 100 = 40,58 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (4672 / 302341) \times 100 = 1,55 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (297669 / 302341) \times 100 = 98,45 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
 RR (necessary condition) = 1,84518030
 RR (sufficient condition) = 1,23271710
 Relative risk reduction (RRR) = -84,52 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
 Odds ratio (OR) = 1,86153271
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,22829999

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(IOU) = 0,39032748$
 $p(IOI) = 0,57876702$

⁴¹Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Annual smoking-attributable mortality, years of potential life lost, and productivity losses—United States, 1997-2001. MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep. 2005 Jul 1;54(25):625-8. PMID: 15988406.

⁴²Barukčić I. Smoking of tobacco is the cause of human lung cancer. JDDT [Internet]. 15Feb.2019 [cited 14Jan.2023];9(1-s):148-60. Available from: <https://jddtonline.info/index.php/jddt/article/view/2273>

Vikas Khurana et al. ⁴³ (see table 2) provided data about the relationship between smoking and lung cancer. As long as we are allowed to rely on the data of Khurana et al. we have to accept the null hypothesis:

without smoking of tobacco, **no** lung cancer.

But is this really the last word on the subject? The study design with $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,3903274$ was very unfair. The placebo group with Not A = 122 684 subjects is about 40 times greater than allowed. Under fair conditions of study design, the number of subject which developed lung cancer without smoking would reduce from $c = 1262$ to about $c = 30$ while the necessary condition relationship would become approximately as $(1-(30/(179657+3000))) = 0,999835758$ with a P Value = 0,000164242. In other words, under optimal conditions, the necessary condition relationship between smoking of tobacco and human lung cancer is much stronger than suggested by the data of Khurana et al. Therefore, one may consider it right or wrong, the data of the study of Khurana et al. support the null hypothesis:

without smoking of tobacco, **no** human lung cancer ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,9958259$; P value = 0,00416540).

Smoking of tobacco is a necessary condition of human lung cancer. If this is true, how can people get lung cancer without being active smokers themselves? In this case, there should not be a single patient who suffers from lung cancer but has not smoked. However, Khurana et al. identified 1262 patients who did not smoke and yet developed lung cancer. However, to get to the heart of the issue, one must need to admit that lung cancer in never-smokers ⁴⁴ · ⁴⁵ (LCINS) questions in principle the importance of smoking as a necessary condition of lung cancer. For whatever reason, in science, we are dealing with P Values. With a P Value = 0,00416540, it seems appropriate enough to accept the null hypothesis.

⁴³Khurana V, Bejjanki HR, Caldito G, Owens MW. Statins reduce the risk of lung cancer in humans: a large case-control study of US veterans. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1282-8. doi: 10.1378/chest.06-0931. PMID: 17494779.

⁴⁴Sun S, Schiller JH, Gazdar AF. Lung cancer in never smokers—a different disease. *Nat Rev Cancer*. 2007 Oct;7(10):778-90. doi: 10.1038/nrc2190. PMID: 17882278.

⁴⁵Torok S, Hegedus B, Laszlo V, Hoda MA, Ghanim B, Berger W, Klepetko W, Dome B, Ostoros G. Lung cancer in never smokers. *Future Oncol*. 2011 Oct;7(10):1195-211. doi: 10.2217/fon.11.100. PMID: 21992731.

3.3. CMV and lung cancer

Searching the PubMed electronic database on the association between CMV and LC, we could not identify one single appropriate case-control or other pertinent study on this relationship. We must therefore limit ourselves to purely theoretical considerations at this point. Nonetheless, currently we do possess additional and reliable methods⁴⁶ which allow us to **make inferences from the known to the unknown** in a logically consistent way. Nevertheless, detailed studies are desirable in this respect, which should be able to allow us to clarify the matter ultimately.

Theorem 1 (CMV infection and lung cancer). *Without CMV infection, no lung cancer.*

Proof by modus ponens. In the following let us consider the following:

Let

$Condition_1 = C_1 = (A_t \leftarrow B_t) = \text{without CMV infection no smoking of tobacco}$ (see table 1)

Let

$Condition_2 = C_2 = (B_t \leftarrow C_t) = \text{without smoking of tobacco no lung cancer}$ (see table 2)

Let

Premise = P = $C_1 \wedge C_2 = ((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) = \text{true}$

Let

Conclusion = C = $(A_t \leftarrow C_t) = \text{without CMV infection no lung cancer} = \text{true}$

In the following, we are applying theorem 7: $(((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t))$ of the publication Single and compound conditions⁴⁷, Version 2 or modus ponens

if

Premise = P = true (1)

then

Conclusion = C = true (2)

In this context, let A_t denote the CMV infection, let B_t denote smoking of tobacco, let C_t denote human lung cancer. We found that condition₁ or **without** CMV infection, **no** smoking of tobacco (see table 1) is true. Furthermore, we found that condition₂ or **without** smoking of tobacco **no** human lung cancer (see table 2) is also true. In other words,

Premise = P = true (3)

⁴⁶Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Single and compound conditions. *Causation*, 18(10), 5–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535107>

⁴⁷Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Single and compound conditions. *Causation*, 18(10), 5–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535107>, p. 24.

Therefore,

$$\text{Conclusion} = C = \text{without CMV infection, no lung cancer} = \text{true} \quad (4)$$

is given too. \square

In considering all these stated circumstances, according to theorem 7 (see Single and compound conditions ⁴⁸, Version 2), the following logical conclusion is inevitable and mandatorily:

If the premise is true, then the conclusion:

without CMV infection, **no** human lung cancer

is also true. In any event, however, it cannot be emphasized strongly enough that we have every reason for supposing that a CMV infection is causally involved in lung cancer. Be that as it may, one can hardly repeat it often enough that almost all of the research carried out in this publication on the relationship between CMV and LC stands and falls with the quality of data of Li et al. ⁴⁹ and with the quality of data of Vikas Khurana et al. ⁵⁰.

⁴⁸Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Single and compound conditions. *Causation*, 18(10), 5–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535107>, p. 24.

⁴⁹Li Z, Tang Y, Tang N, Feng Q, Zhong H, Liu YM, Wang LM, He F. High anti-human cytomegalovirus antibody levels are associated with the progression of essential hypertension and target organ damage in Han Chinese population. *PLoS One*. 2017 Aug 24;12(8):e0181440. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0181440. PMID: 28837559; PMCID: PMC5570371.

⁵⁰Khurana V, Bejjanki HR, Caldito G, Owens MW. Statins reduce the risk of lung cancer in humans: a large case-control study of US veterans. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1282-8. doi: 10.1378/chest.06-0931. PMID: 17494779.

3.4. CMV and LC

The data and the statistical analysis of the data of the study of Kuo et al. ⁵¹ (Chest Division, Medical Department, Mackay Memorial Hospital, Taipei, Taiwan) are presented by table 3.

Table 3. CMV and Lung cancer (Study of Kuo et al., 2008).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
CMV DNA	YES	2	12	14
	NO	0	1	1
		2	13	15

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = +0,10482848$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,86666667
p (SINE) = 1,00000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 1,00000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 1,00000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,86666667
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,00
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,00
P Value (SINE) = 0,00000000

PROPORTIONS.

(a/A) × 100 = (2 / 14) × 100 = 14,29 %
(b/A) × 100 = (12 / 14) × 100 = 85,71 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (0 / 1) × 100 = 0,00 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (1 / 1) × 100 = 100,00 %
(a/B) × 100 = (2 / 2) × 100 = 100,00 %
(c/B) × 100 = (0 / 2) × 100 = 0,00 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (12 / 13) × 100 = 92,31 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (1 / 13) × 100 = 7,69 %
(A/N) × 100 = (14 / 15) × 100 = 93,33 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (1 / 15) × 100 = 6,67 %
(B/N) × 100 = (2 / 15) × 100 = 13,33 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (13 / 15) × 100 = 86,67 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = Division by zero!
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,08333333

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = Division by zero!
Index of relationship (IOR) = +0,07142857

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,06666667
p(IOI)= 0,80000000

⁵¹Kuo CP, Wu CL, Ho HT, Chen CG, Liu SI, Lu YT. Detection of cytomegalovirus reactivation in cancer patients receiving chemotherapy. Clin Microbiol Infect. 2008 Mar;14(3):221-7. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-0691.2007.01895.x. Epub 2007 Dec 5. PMID: 18070129, p. 223.

The CMV prevalence in the non lung cancer control group is $(b / \text{not } B) \times 100 = (12 / 13) \times 100 = 92,31 \%$ and is very close to the prevalence in the normal population. The data of Kuo et al. are not extremely biased ($p(\text{IOU})=0,06666667$). The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,00 and the $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,00. In other words, we accept the null-hypothesis: **without** CMV infection, **no** lung cancer and reject the alternative hypothesis. In contrast to the previous and pure theoretical considerations, Kuo et al. provided hard, PCR based evidence that **a CMV infection is a necessary condition of lung cancer**.

Nonetheless, a very critical reader may note that all these data were collected under the influence of chemotherapy and therefore are only of limited value. However, such or similar counter-arguments cannot really be taken seriously. Whether, and what influence chemotherapy might have on CMV infection, is not the point of issue in this context. In particular, chemotherapy is neither a necessary condition nor the cause of a CMV infection.

There is no possible exception to the relationship of a necessary condition and the majority of reader will agree that only one ($n = 1$) counter-example is enough to dismiss a theory, a hypothesis or a necessary condition relationship et cetera. However, the sample size of the study of Kuo et al. is a counter-argument on its own, the sample size of the study of Kuo et al. is too small. In general, what sample size is small depends on the context, too. Research in human medicine cannot always ensure extremely precise conditions which can be reproduced exactly and without any errors or problems at all times and everywhere. Subjective as well as objective factors such as a variation of pathogen, host and environmental factors and their interaction can theoretically invalidate a theory, a hypothesis et cetera at any time. Therefore, a small sample size might have a greater negative influence on research outcomes than a big sample size, but need not. As generally known, samples should not be either too small or too big, since both might compromise the conclusions drawn from a study. Whatever one's basic attitude might be, the belief that one can draw a precise and accurate conclusion only with an appropriate and big sample size is not justified. The data of the pilot study of Kuo et al. may not represent the last word in wisdom on the relationship between CMV and LC, but these data cannot be ignored either. Therefore, until there is evidence to the contrary, it is provisionally presumed, that a CMV infection is a necessary condition of lung cancer. In other words,

without CMV infection, **no** human lung cancer.

(p (SINE) = 1,0; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,0; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,0; P Value (SINE) = 0,0)

Despite all misgivings, there is another and good logical reason for this scientific evidence. The study group of Balthesen et al. ⁵² found that the lungs are one major organ site of cytomegalovirus latency and recurrence.

⁵²Balthesen M, Messerle M, Reddehase MJ. Lungs are a major organ site of cytomegalovirus latency and recurrence. *J Virol.* 1993 Sep;67(9):5360-6. doi: 10.1128/JVI.67.9.5360-5366.1993. PMID: 8394453; PMCID: PMC237936.

3.5. CMV and treatment

The following proposal of a treatment of a CMV infection should be initiated, supervised and monitored by a medical specialist experienced with the drugs suggested. The scientific justification for the proposed medications follows as next.

Table 4. CMV infection: Additional therapy

Data:	Name	First name	Birthday	Place of residence	Phone	E-Mail	Approved by
Drug	Immunoglobulin	Leflunomide	Etoricoxib	Etanercept	Valaciclovir	Atorvastatin	Cimetidin
Dosage	1 g per kg i.v. qd	10 mg qd or 20 mg p.o. qd	30 mg or 90 mg p.o. qd	10 mg or 25 mg or 50 mg s.c.	2 g p. o. qid	80 mg qd	800 mg qd
Month:							
Day:							
1	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
2		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
3	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
4		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
5	Yes	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
6		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
7		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
8		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0 s. c.		0-0-1	1-0-0-0
9		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
10		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
11		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
12		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
13		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
14		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
15		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
16		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
17		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
18		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
19		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
20		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
21		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0		1-1-1-1	0-0-1	1-0-0-0
22		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0 s. c.		0-0-1	1-0-0-0
23		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
24		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
25		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
26		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
27		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
28		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
29		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
30		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0
31		1-0-0-0	1-0-0-0			0-0-1	1-0-0-0

Abbreviations. q.i.d.: quater in die (four times a day). t.i.d.: ter in die (three times a day). b.i.d.: bis in die (twice a day). q.d.: quaque die (once a day).

3.5.1. CMV and Immunoglobulin

Intravenous immunoglobulin (IV IgG) therapy (1 g per kilogram per day for 2-3 days) against COVID-19 infection has been demonstrated to be clinically effective.⁵³,⁵⁴,⁵⁵ There is no reasonable argument to assume why this should be different for CMV. The use of CMV immunoglobulin⁵⁶ (CMVIG) is also a possible option. Dosage would also depend on the severity of the disease, while measures of clinical, laboratory (CMV antibodies) and other monitoring are of high importance in each case. Feinstein et al.⁵⁷ investigated whether intravenous immunoglobulin given at a dose of 500 mg/kg/wk might decrease the risk of a CMV infection (see table 5).

Table 5. The relationship between IV IgG and CMV infection (Study of Feinstein et al., 1999).

		CMV infection		
		YES	NO	
IV IgG	YES	3	117	120
	NO	10	111	121
		13	228	241

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship k = -0,12758601
p (EXCL) = 0,98755187
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,04318195
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,01237098

However, I consider it quite remarkable that Feinstein et al. were able to provide statistically significant evidence that intravenous immunoglobulin given at a dose of 500 mg/kg/wk does decrease the risk of a CMV infection (**p (EXCL) = 0,98755187; P Value (EXCL) = 0,01237098**).

3.5.2. CMV and Leflunomide

Cytomegalovirus (CMV) infections are associated with increased morbidity and mortality and poses a major challenge for patient and physicians. Leflunomide or (N-(4'-trifluoromethylphenyl)-5-methylisoxazole-4-carboxamide) is an inhibitor of protein kinase activity and pyrimidine synthesis

⁵³Schultz NH, Sørvoll IH, Michelsen AE, Munthe LA, Lund-Johansen F, Ahlen MT, Wiedmann M, Aamodt AH, Skattør TH, Tjønnfjord GE, Holme PA. Thrombosis and Thrombocytopenia after ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 Vaccination. *N Engl J Med.* 2021 Jun 3;384(22):2124-2130. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2104882. Epub 2021 Apr 9. PMID: 33835768; PMCID: PMC8112568.

⁵⁴Barukčić, Ilija. (2021, April 18). Comment on Thrombosis and Thrombocytopenia after ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 Vaccination (Version 2). Version 2. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4707741>

⁵⁵Xiang HR, Cheng X, Li Y, Luo WW, Zhang QZ, Peng WX. Efficacy of IVIG (intravenous immunoglobulin) for corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19): A meta-analysis. *Int Immunopharmacol.* 2021 Jul;96:107732. doi: 10.1016/j.intimp.2021.107732. Epub 2021 Apr 30. PMID: 34162133; PMCID: PMC8084608.

⁵⁶Santhanakrishnan K, Yonan N, Iyer K, Callan P, Al-Aloul M, Venkateswaran R. Management of ganciclovir resistance cytomegalovirus infection with CMV hyperimmune globulin and leflunomide in seven cardiothoracic transplant recipients and literature review. *Transpl Infect Dis.* 2022 Feb;24(1):e13733. doi: 10.1111/tid.13733. Epub 2021 Oct 5. PMID: 34534396.

⁵⁷Feinstein LC, Seidel K, Jocum J, Bowden RA, Anasetti C, Deeg HJ, Flowers ME, Kansu E, Martin PJ, Nash RA, Storek J, Etzioni R, Applebaum FR, Hansen JA, Storb R, Sullivan KM. Reduced dose intravenous immunoglobulin does not decrease transplant-related complications in adults given related donor marrow allografts. *Biol Blood Marrow Transplant.* 1999;5(6):369-78. doi: 10.1016/s1083-8791(99)70013-3. PMID: 10595814.

and is easily given orally. Leflunomide works by inhibiting virion assembly.^{58 59} It has been shown that Leflunomide is effective^{60 61} against cases of CMV infection too.^{62 , 63 , 64}

3.5.3. CMV and Etanercept

It is known that tumour necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) is able to mediate host-resistance against micro-organisms and inhibits at the end CMV replication. Especially, serum TNF- α is found to be elevated during acute CMV-infections.⁶⁵ Unfortunately, tumour necrosis factor alpha is a very powerful cytokine with a very ‘dark side’ too. It is now clear that TNF- α is involved causally in various pathological processes including malignant disease.⁶⁶ Anti-tumour necrosis factor alpha antibody therapy with TNF- α blocking agents like etanercept^{67 , 68}, infliximab and adalimumab provide a strategic option to block the pivotal role of TNF- α in the pathological pathway of (lung) cancer. In the case that a relationship between CMV and LC can be established, serum TNF- α could be of use to monitor LC therapy.

3.5.4. CMV and Valacyclovir

Currently available options for CMV treatment and prophylaxis present various challenges related to cost and side effects. Stephanie Lam (Department of Haematology, Fiona Stanley Hospital, Perth, Australia) et al. investigated whether prophylaxis with high dose valaciclovir is effective at reducing CMV infection. Patients were treated with 2g valaciclovir orally four times daily. “Forty-nine patients

⁵⁸Waldman WJ, Knight DA, Blinder L, Shen J, Lurain NS, Miller DM, Sedmak DD, Williams JW, Chong AS. Inhibition of cytomegalovirus in vitro and in vivo by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Intervirology*. 1999;42(5-6):412-8. doi: 10.1159/000053979. PMID: 10702725.

⁵⁹Waldman WJ, Knight DA, Lurain NS, Miller DM, Sedmak DD, Williams JW, Chong AS. Novel mechanism of inhibition of cytomegalovirus by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Transplantation*. 1999 Sep 27;68(6):814-25. doi: 10.1097/00007890-199909270-00014. PMID: 10515382.

⁶⁰John GT, Manivannan J, Chandy S, Peter S, Jacob CK. Leflunomide therapy for cytomegalovirus disease in renal allograft recipients. *Transplantation*. 2004 May 15;77(9):1460-1. doi: 10.1097/01.tp.0000122185.64004.89. PMID: 15167608.

⁶¹Avery RK, Bolwell BJ, Yen-Lieberman B, Lurain N, Waldman WJ, Longworth DL, Taeye AJ, Mossad SB, Kohn D, Long JR, Curtis J, Kalaycio M, Pohlman B, Williams JW. Use of leflunomide in an allogeneic bone marrow transplant recipient with refractory cytomegalovirus infection. *Bone Marrow Transplant*. 2004 Dec;34(12):1071-5. doi: 10.1038/sj.bmt.1704694. PMID: 15489872.

⁶²Sudarsanam TD, Sahni RD, John GT. Leflunomide: a possible alternative for ganciclovir sensitive and resistant cytomegalovirus infections. *Postgrad Med J*. 2006 May;82(967):313-4. doi: 10.1136/pgmj.2005.038521. PMID: 16679469; PMCID: PMC2563786.

⁶³John GT, Manivannan J, Chandy S, Peter S, Jacob CK. Leflunomide therapy for cytomegalovirus disease in renal allograft recipients. *Transplantation*. 2004 May 15;77(9):1460-1. doi: 10.1097/01.tp.0000122185.64004.89. PMID: 15167608.

⁶⁴Suissa S, Bernatsky S, Hudson M. Antirheumatic drug use and the risk of acute myocardial infarction. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2006 Aug 15;55(4):531-6. doi: 10.1002/art.22094. PMID: 16874796.

⁶⁵Haerter G, Manfras BJ, de Jong-Hesse Y, Wilts H, Mertens T, Kern P, Schmitt M. Cytomegalovirus retinitis in a patient treated with anti-tumor necrosis factor alpha antibody therapy for rheumatoid arthritis. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2004 Nov 1;39(9):e88-94. doi: 10.1086/425123. Epub 2004 Oct 11. PMID: 15494900.

⁶⁶Balkwill F. TNF-alpha in promotion and progression of cancer. *Cancer Metastasis Rev*. 2006 Sep;25(3):409-16. doi: 10.1007/s10555-006-9005-3. PMID: 16951987.

⁶⁷Hung YM, Lin L, Chen CM, Chiou JY, Wang YH, Wang PY, Wei JC. The effect of anti-rheumatic medications for coronary artery diseases risk in patients with rheumatoid arthritis might be changed over time: A nationwide population-based cohort study. *PLoS One*. 2017 Jun 28;12(6):e0179081. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0179081. PMID: 28658301; PMCID: PMC5489160.

⁶⁸Barukčić, Ilija. (2020). Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of human atherosclerosis. *International Journal Of Current Science Research*. Volume: 6; Issue: 1; January-2020; pp 1912-1938. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3902775>

in the prophylaxis group and 59 in the control group were included ... There was no CMV disease in the prophylaxis group and three cases in the control group. ⁶⁹ In other words, **without treatment with 2g valaciclovir orally four times daily no absence of a CMV infection**. Hawks et al. found that valacyclovir 1 g three times daily with affordable cost and a favourable toxicity profile is an option for CMV prophylaxis ⁷⁰ and therapy too. ⁷¹

3.5.5. CMV and Cimetidine

Cimetidine is an H₂ receptor antagonist ⁷² with the indication of gastroesophageal reflux disease, peptic ulcer disease, urticaria, and other. Cimetidine affects even the pharmacokinetics of other drugs. The effects of cimetidine, probenecid and of other drugs on the pharmacokinetics of valacyclovir have been investigated. ⁷³ Cimetidine (800 mg bid) inhibit excretion of valacyclovir and, thus, potentiate antiviral concentrations of serum while not affecting the tolerability of valacyclovir. ⁷⁴, ⁷⁵

3.5.6. CMV and Etoricoxib

Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) is an enzyme involved in pain and inflammation. Selective inhibitors of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) might downregulate COX-2 and decrease inflammation and pain. Etoricoxib ⁷⁶ as member of the class of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) is a highly selective inhibitor of cyclooxygenase-2. The long plasma half-life of etoricoxib allows the use of etoricoxib ⁷⁷

⁶⁹Lam S, Boan P, Polistena P, Cannell P, Cooney J, Wright M, Purtill D. High dose valaciclovir to prevent cytomegalovirus infection in allogeneic haematopoietic stem cell transplant recipients. *Transpl Infect Dis*. 2021 Aug;23(4):e13633. doi: 10.1111/tid.13633. Epub 2021 Jun 1. PMID: 33978289.

⁷⁰Hawks KG, Fegley A, Sabo RT, Roberts CH, Toor AA. High dose valacyclovir for cytomegalovirus prophylaxis following allogeneic hematopoietic cell transplantation. *J Oncol Pharm Pract*. 2023 Jan;29(1):130-137. doi: 10.1177/10781552211060479. Epub 2021 Dec 2. PMID: 34854771.

⁷¹Shahar-Nissan K, Pardo J, Peled O, Krause I, Bilavsky E, Wiznitzer A, Hadar E, Amir J. Valaciclovir to prevent vertical transmission of cytomegalovirus after maternal primary infection during pregnancy: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2020 Sep 12;396(10253):779-785. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31868-7. Erratum in: *Lancet*. 2020 Oct 10;396(10257):1070. PMID: 32919517.

⁷²Pino MA, Azer SA. Cimetidine. 2022 May 1. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan-. PMID: 31334975.

⁷³De Bony F, Tod M, Bidault R, On NT, Posner J, Rolan P. Multiple interactions of cimetidine and probenecid with valaciclovir and its metabolite acyclovir. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*. 2002 Feb;46(2):458-63. doi: 10.1128/AAC.46.2.458-463.2002. PMID: 11796358; PMCID: PMC127018.

⁷⁴Lerner AM, Beqaj SH, Deeter RG, Fitzgerald JT. Valacyclovir treatment in Epstein-Barr virus subset chronic fatigue syndrome: thirty-six months follow-up. *In Vivo*. 2007 Sep-Oct;21(5):707-13. PMID: 18019402.

⁷⁵Purifoy DJ, Beauchamp LM, de Miranda P, Ertl P, Lacey S, Roberts G, Rahim SG, Darby G, Krenitsky TA, Powell KL. Review of research leading to new anti-herpesvirus agents in clinical development: valaciclovir hydrochloride (256U, the L-valyl ester of acyclovir) and 882C, a specific agent for varicella zoster virus. *J Med Virol*. 1993;Suppl 1:139-45. doi: 10.1002/jmv.1890410527. PMID: 8245881.

⁷⁶Ong SWX, Tan WYT, Chan YH, Fong SW, Renia L, Ng LF, Leo YS, Lye DC, Young BE. Safety and potential efficacy of cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors in coronavirus disease 2019. *Clin Transl Immunology*. 2020 Jul 26;9(7):e1159. doi: 10.1002/cti2.1159. PMID: 32728438; PMCID: PMC7382954.

⁷⁷Wu LC, Leong PY, Yeo KJ, Li TY, Wang YH, Chiou JY, Wei JC. Celecoxib and sulfasalazine had negative association with coronary artery diseases in patients with ankylosing spondylitis: A nation-wide, population-based case-control study. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2016 Sep;95(36):e4792. doi: 10.1097/MD.0000000000004792. PMID: 27603385; PMCID: PMC5023908.

· ⁷⁸ for once-daily dosing. ⁷⁹ The study group around Hung et al. provided some **very slight and indirect evidence** that etoricoxib is of help against CMV infection too. ⁸⁰ Further investigations are needed to decipher the relationship between etoricoxib and CMV infection in its entirety.

⁷⁸Barukčić, Ilija. (2020). Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of human atherosclerosis. *International Journal Of Current Science Research*. Volume: 6; Issue: 1; January-2020; pp 1912-1938. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3902775>

⁷⁹Matsumoto AK, Cavanaugh PF Jr. Etoricoxib. *Drugs Today (Barc)*. 2004 May;40(5):395-414. PMID: 15319795.

⁸⁰Hung YM, Lin L, Chen CM, Chiou JY, Wang YH, Wang PY, Wei JC. The effect of anti-rheumatic medications for coronary artery diseases risk in patients with rheumatoid arthritis might be changed over time: A nationwide population-based cohort study. *PLoS One*. 2017 Jun 28;12(6):e0179081. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0179081. PMID: 28658301; PMCID: PMC5489160.

3.5.7. Statins and lung cancer

Statins are commonly used drugs to lower cholesterol levels through inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme (HMG-CoA) reductase. Benjamin D Horne et al. evaluated in a prospective study the effect of statins on CMV and found that statins have beneficial antiinflammatory effects⁸¹ while a direct antiviral effect of statin is not completely out of the realm of possibility. Meanwhile, the potential anticancer effects⁸² of statins and the statin reduced⁸³,⁸⁴ cancer-related mortality attracted increasing attention of scholars. Simvastatin demonstrated more benefits for lung cancer patients than pravastatin.⁸⁵,⁸⁶ Even Atorvastatin had potential anticancer effects.⁸⁷,⁸⁸ However, inconsistent results on these relationship have been reported too. Atorvastatin⁸⁹,⁹⁰ (AVT), is able to suppress⁹¹ tumour⁹²,⁹³ cell growth too and is potentially protective⁹⁴ against the development of lung⁹⁵ cancer.

3.5.7.1. The study of Khurana et al., 2007, USA Vikas Khurana et al.⁹⁶ investigated in a retrospective case-control study (N = 483,733 patients) whether the use of statins prior to the diagnosis

⁸¹Horne BD, Muhlestein JB, Carlquist JF, Bair TL, Madsen TE, Hart NI, Anderson JL; Intermountain Heart Collaborative (IHC) Study Group. Statin therapy interacts with cytomegalovirus seropositivity and high C-reactive protein in reducing mortality among patients with angiographically significant coronary disease. *Circulation*. 2003 Jan 21;107(2):258-63. doi: 10.1161/01.cir.0000045668.71683.92. PMID: 12538425.

⁸²Xia DK, Hu ZG, Tian YF, Zeng FJ. Statin use and prognosis of lung cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies and randomized controlled trials. *Drug Des Devel Ther*. 2019 Jan 23;13:405-422. doi: 10.2147/DDDT.S187690. PMID: 30774306; PMCID: PMC6350654.

⁸³Nielsen SF, Nordestgaard BG, Bojesen SE. Statin use and reduced cancer-related mortality. *N Engl J Med*. 2012 Nov 8;367(19):1792-802. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1201735. PMID: 23134381.

⁸⁴Li X, Wu XB, Chen Q. Statin use is not associated with reduced risk of skin cancer: a meta-analysis. *Br J Cancer*. 2014 Feb 4;110(3):802-7. doi: 10.1038/bjc.2013.762. Epub 2013 Dec 24. PMID: 24366301; PMCID: PMC3915126.

⁸⁵Cardwell CR, Mc Menamin Ú, Hughes CM, Murray LJ. Statin use and survival from lung cancer: a population-based cohort study. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev*. 2015 May;24(5):833-41. doi: 10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-15-0052. PMID: 25934831.

⁸⁶Hwang KE, Kwon SJ, Kim YS, Park DS, Kim BR, Yoon KH, Jeong ET, Kim HR. Effect of simvastatin on the resistance to EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitors in a non-small cell lung cancer with the T790M mutation of EGFR. *Exp Cell Res*. 2014 May 1;323(2):288-96. doi: 10.1016/j.yexcr.2014.02.026. Epub 2014 Mar 12. PMID: 24631288.

⁸⁷Chen J, Liu B, Yuan J, Yang J, Zhang J, An Y, Tie L, Pan Y, Li X. Atorvastatin reduces vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) expression in human non-small cell lung carcinomas (NSCLCs) via inhibition of reactive oxygen species (ROS) production. *Mol Oncol*. 2012 Feb;6(1):62-72. doi: 10.1016/j.molonc.2011.11.003. Epub 2011 Nov 22. PMID: 22153388; PMCID: PMC5528383.

⁸⁸Chen J, Lan T, Hou J, Zhang J, An Y, Tie L, Pan Y, Liu J, Li X. Atorvastatin sensitizes human non-small cell lung carcinomas to carboplatin via suppression of AKT activation and upregulation of TIMP-1. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol*. 2012 May;44(5):759-69. doi: 10.1016/j.biocel.2012.01.015. Epub 2012 Jan 25. PMID: 22305890.

⁸⁹Lin JJ, Ezer N, Sigel K, Mhango G, Wisnivesky JP. The effect of statins on survival in patients with stage IV lung cancer. *Lung Cancer*. 2016 Sep;99:137-42. doi: 10.1016/j.lungcan.2016.07.006. Epub 2016 Jul 6. PMID: 27565929; PMCID: PMC5003323.

⁹⁰Xia DK, Hu ZG, Tian YF, Zeng FJ. Statin use and prognosis of lung cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies and randomized controlled trials. *Drug Des Devel Ther*. 2019 Jan 23;13:405-422. doi: 10.2147/DDDT.S187690. PMID: 30774306; PMCID: PMC6350654.

⁹¹Vallianou NG, Kostantinou A, Kougias M, Kazazis C. Statins and cancer. *Anticancer Agents Med Chem*. 2014 Jun;14(5):706-12. doi: 10.2174/1871520613666131129105035. PMID: 24295174.

⁹²Cafforio P, Dammacco F, Gernone A, Silvestris F. Statins activate the mitochondrial pathway of apoptosis in human lymphoblasts and myeloma cells. *Carcinogenesis*. 2005 May;26(5):883-91. doi: 10.1093/carcin/bgi036. Epub 2005 Feb 10. PMID: 15705602.

⁹³Kaushal V, Kohli M, Mehta P, Mehta JL. Potential anticancer effects of statins: fact or fiction? *Endothelium*. 2003;10(1):49-58. doi: 10.1080/106233203033358. PMID: 12699077.

⁹⁴Gray J, Alberts WM, Bepler G. Statins and lung cancer risk. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1274-5. doi: 10.1378/chest.07-0308. PMID: 17494775.

⁹⁵<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8720807/>

⁹⁶Khurana V, Bejjanki HR, Caldito G, Owens MW. Statins reduce the risk of lung cancer in humans: a large case-control study of US veterans. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1282-8. doi: 10.1378/chest.06-0931. PMID: 17494779.

of lung cancer has any protective effect against the development of lung cancer. The accuracy of the intake of the medication was not guaranteed. Still, Vikas Khurana et al. found that the protective effect of statin therapy against lung cancer increased with the duration of statin therapy. Among those who used statin for 4 years and more there was a 77% reduction for lung cancer.

Table 6. Statin therapy (> 4 year) and lung cancer (Study of Khurana et al., 2007).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy > 4 year	YES	269	49739	50008
	NO	7011	426714	433725
		7280	476453	483733

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,02697061$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,99944391
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,99462086
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,96304945

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 1,44698848
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 9,93969780
P Value (EXCL) = 0,00055594

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (269 / 50008) \times 100 = 0,54 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (49739 / 50008) \times 100 = 99,46 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (7011 / 433725) \times 100 = 1,62 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (426714 / 433725) \times 100 = 98,38 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (269 / 7280) \times 100 = 3,70 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (7011 / 7280) \times 100 = 96,30 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (49739 / 476453) \times 100 = 10,44 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (426714 / 476453) \times 100 = 89,56 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (50008 / 483733) \times 100 = 10,34 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (433725 / 483733) \times 100 = 89,66 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (7280 / 483733) \times 100 = 1,50 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (476453 / 483733) \times 100 = 98,50 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,33277239
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,35395163
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 66,72 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,32916387
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,64257319

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,88157103
p(IOI) = 0,08832972

The study design (p(IOI) = 0,08832972) of the study of Khurana et al. was suitable enough, but not optimal. In the optimal case, the placebo group should have been enlarged up to 7 times more to a sample size of 3.000.000 million subjects. In other words, the exclusion relationship between statin therapy > 4 years and lung cancer will be much stronger than suggested by the data of the study of Khurana et al. It should be noted, however, that a long-term therapy with statins is almost as effective against lung cancer (p(EXCL)= 0,99944391; P Value = 0,00055594) as a vaccination with Pfizer/Biontech's mRNA vaccine against Covid 19 (p(EXCL)= 1-(8/43448) = 0,999815872; P Value =

0,000184128).⁹⁷,⁹⁸ This is quite a surprising result, and we understandably ask ourselves how this can be? Does the data of Khurana et al. represent objective reality very accurately? More or less, it seems to be that statins have anti-inflammatory properties.

3.5.7.2. The study of Kang et al., 2014, South Korea Kang et al.⁹⁹ conducted a retrospective cohort study based on the South Korean nationwide claims database to evaluate whether statin use affects the development¹⁰⁰ of tuberculosis (TB). The data published by Kang et al. (see table 7) support the claim that statin use excludes the development of tuberculosis with a probability of $p(\text{EXCL}) = (1 - (504/(840899))) = 0.99940064$ (P Value = 0.00059918).

Table 7. Statin therapy and Tuberculosis (Study of Kang et al., 2014).

		Tuberculosis		
		YES	NO	
Statins	YES	504	158694	159198
	NO	3571	678130	681701
		4075	836824	840899
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.				
		Causal relationship k =	-0,01169174	
		P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) =	0,00000000	
		p (EXCL) =	0,99940064	
		P Value (EXCL) =	0,00059918	
		p(IOI)=	0,18447281	

Therefore, statins are potentially effective against *Mycobacterium avium* subspecies paratuberculosis (MAP) and of use for Morbus Crohn too. Incredibly amazing, several publications support our belief that statins have beneficial anti-inflammatory properties, especially against CMV¹⁰¹, including the study of Benjamin D Horne et al.¹⁰² Under the justified assumption that this more than just theoretically possible relationship can be confirmed by other study groups too, another question is straightforward and mandatory. Is there any causal influence of CMV on lung cancer?¹⁰³

⁹⁷Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, Absalon J, Gurtman A, Lockhart S, Perez JL, Pérez Marc G, Moreira ED, Zerbini C, Bailey R, Swanson KA, Roychoudhury S, Koury K, Li P, Kalina WV, Cooper D, Frenck RW Jr, Hammitt LL, Türeci Ö, Nell H, Schaefer A, Ünal S, Tresnan DB, Mather S, Dormitzer PR, Şahin U, Jansen KU, Gruber WC; C4591001 Clinical Trial Group. Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med.* 2020 Dec 31;383(27):2603-2615. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2034577. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33301246; PMCID: PMC7745181.

⁹⁸Barukčić, Ilija. (2021). COVID-19 vaccines - a great leap forward?. *Causation*, 6(12), 5–53. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779506>, p. 42.

⁹⁹Kang YA, Choi NK, Seong JM, Heo EY, Koo BK, Hwang SS, Park BJ, Yim JJ, Lee CH. The effects of statin use on the development of tuberculosis among patients with diabetes mellitus. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis.* 2014 Jun;18(6):717-24. doi: 10.5588/ijtld.13.0854. Erratum in: *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis.* 2015 May;19(5):622. PMID: 24903944.

¹⁰⁰Guerra-De-Blas PDC, Torres-González P, Bobadilla-Del-Valle M, Sada-Ovalle I, Ponce-De-León-Garduño A, Sifuentes-Osorio J. Potential Effect of Statins on *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* Infection. *J Immunol Res.* 2018 Nov 15;2018:7617023. doi: 10.1155/2018/7617023. PMID: 30581876; PMCID: PMC6276473.

¹⁰¹Ponroy N, Taveira A, Mueller NJ, Millard AL. Statins demonstrate a broad anti-cytomegalovirus activity in vitro in ganciclovir-susceptible and resistant strains. *J Med Virol.* 2015 Jan;87(1):141-53. doi:10.1002/jmv.23998. Epub 2014 Jun 27. See: PMID: 24976258.

¹⁰²Horne BD, Muhlestein JB, Carlquist JF, Bair TL, Madsen TE, Hart NI, Anderson JL; Intermountain Heart Collaborative (IHC) Study Group. Statin therapy interacts with cytomegalovirus seropositivity and high C-reactive protein in reducing mortality among patients with angiographically significant coronary disease. *Circulation.* 2003 Jan 21;107(2):258-63. doi: 10.1161/01.cir.0000045668.71683.92. PMID: 12538425.

¹⁰³Du X, Li D, Wang G, Fan Y, Li N, Chai L, Li G, Li J. Chemoprotective effect of atorvastatin against benzo(a)pyrene-induced lung cancer via the inhibition of oxidative stress and inflammatory parameters. *Ann Transl Med.* 2021 Feb;9(4):355. doi: 10.21037/atm-

3.5.7.3. The study of Lui et al., 2017, Taiwan Liu et al. ¹⁰⁴ (Division of Cardiovascular Medicine, Department of Internal Medicine, Shuang Ho Hospital, Taipei Medical University, New Taipei City, Taiwan) conducted a population-based cohort study with 10,086 statin user and 33,716 non-statin user to evaluate the relationship of the use of competitive inhibitors of hydroxymethylglutaryl-coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase (statins) like simvastatin, atorvastatin, lovastatin, fluvastatin (lipophilia statins) and rosuvastatin and pravastatin (hydrophilia statins) with lung cancer risk while using data from the National Health Insurance Research Database (NHIRD). In toto, 159/10086 of statin users suffered from lung cancer, whereas 1225/33716 of non-statin user had lung cancer. Table 8 provides us with an overview of the data collected, as well as the statistical analysis.

Table 8. Statin therapy and lung cancer (Study of Liu et al., 2016).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy	YES	159	9927	10086
	NO	1225	32491	33716
		1384	42418	43802

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship k = -0,04950356
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,99637003
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,98423557
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,88511561
P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 2,50654372
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 18,26661850
P Value (EXCL) = 0,00362339
PROPORTIONS.
(a/A) × 100 = (159 / 10086) × 100 = 1,58 %
(b/A) × 100 = (9927 / 10086) × 100 = 98,42 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (1225 / 33716) × 100 = 3,63 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (32491 / 33716) × 100 = 96,37 %
(a/B) × 100 = (159 / 1384) × 100 = 11,49 %
(c/B) × 100 = (1225 / 1384) × 100 = 88,51 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (9927 / 42418) × 100 = 23,40 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (32491 / 42418) × 100 = 76,60 %
(A/N) × 100 = (10086 / 43802) × 100 = 23,03 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (33716 / 43802) × 100 = 76,97 %
(B/N) × 100 = (1384 / 43802) × 100 = 3,16 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (42418 / 43802) × 100 = 96,84 %
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,43388848
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,49090019
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,42482111
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,50107414
STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,73813981
p(IOI)= 0,19866673

The data of the study are usable. The results are better than the analysis before indicates. The sample also included individual statins like lovastatin and fluvastatin which do not really reduce lung cancer risk significantly. Conclusion. Statins dose-dependently exclude lung cancer (P Value = 0,0).

20-7770. PMID: PMC7944302 PMID: 33708982. Erratum in: Ann Transl Med. 2021 Jul;9(14):1214. PMID: 33708982; PMID: PMC7944302.

¹⁰⁴Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. Oncotarget. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMID: PMC5312335.

3.5.7.3.1. The study of Lui et al., 2017, Taiwan The study of Liu et al. ¹⁰⁵ has been unfair. Under the assumption of conditions of fair study design ($A = B$ or $b = c$ or $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$) and without changing the proportion within the sample itself ($((a/A) = 1,58 \%)$ and $((c/\text{not } A) = 3,63 \%)$), we would obtain the following, fictive data (see table 9).

Table 9. Statin therapy and lung cancer (Study of Liu et al., 2016 (fictive data)).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy	YES	159	9927	10086
	NO	9927	263296	273223
		10086	273223	283309

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = -0,02056853$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,99943878
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,98423557
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,98423557

P VALUES.
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 2,50654372
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 2,50654372
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,00056107

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (159 / 10086) \times 100 = 1,58 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (9927 / 10086) \times 100 = 98,42 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (9927 / 273223) \times 100 = 3,63 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (263296 / 273223) \times 100 = 96,37 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (159 / 10086) \times 100 = 1,58 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (9927 / 10086) \times 100 = 98,42 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (9927 / 273223) \times 100 = 3,63 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (263296 / 273223) \times 100 = 96,37 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (10086 / 283309) \times 100 = 3,56 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (273223 / 283309) \times 100 = 96,44 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (10086 / 283309) \times 100 = 3,56 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (273223 / 283309) \times 100 = 96,44 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
 RR (necessary condition) = 0,43388776
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,43388776

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
 Odds ratio (OR) = 0,42482038
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,55718781

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,92879859$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,00000000$

As long as we have reason to have confidence into the quality of the data of the study of Liu et al., a long-term therapy with statins is almost as effective against lung cancer ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,99943878$; P Value (EXCL) = 0,00056107) as a vaccination with Pfizer/Biontech's mRNA vaccine against Covid 19 ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 1-(8/43448) = 0,999815872$; P Value = 0,000184128) ¹⁰⁶, ¹⁰⁷ viral infection. Noteworthy, these results are comparable with the findings of the study Vikas Khurana et al. ¹⁰⁸ (N = 483733).

¹⁰⁵Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

¹⁰⁶Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, Absalon J, Gurtman A, Lockhart S, Perez JL, Pérez Marc G, Moreira ED, Zerbini C, Bailey R, Swanson KA, Roychoudhury S, Koury K, Li P, Kalina WV, Cooper D, Frenck RW Jr, Hammitt LL, Türeci Ö, Nell H, Schaefer A, Ünal S, Tresnan DB, Mather S, Dormitzer PR, Şahin U, Jansen KU, Gruber WC; C4591001 Clinical Trial Group. Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Dec 31;383(27):2603-2615. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2034577. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33301246; PMCID: PMC7745181.

¹⁰⁷Barukčić, Ilija. (2021). COVID-19 vaccines - a great leap forward?. *Causation*, 6(12), 5–53. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779506>, p. 42.

¹⁰⁸Khurana V, Bejjanki HR, Caldito G, Owens MW. Statins reduce the risk of lung cancer in humans: a large case-control study of

3.5.7.3.2. Pravastatin and lung cancer Liu et al. ¹⁰⁹ provided data about the relationship between pravastatin and lung cancer (see table 10).

Table 10. Relationship: pravastatin and lung cancer (Study of Liu et al. , 2016).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Pravastatin	YES	19	1482	1501
	NO	1365	40936	42301
		1384	42418	43802

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,02039443$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000131
 p (EXCL) = 0,99956623
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,98734177$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,98627168$

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000131
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 0,24050633
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 0,26083815
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,00043368

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (19 / 43802) \times 100 = 0,04 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (1482 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,38 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1365 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,12 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (40936 / 43802) \times 100 = 93,46 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (19 / 1501) \times 100 = 1,27 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (1482 / 1501) \times 100 = 98,73 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (1365 / 42301) \times 100 = 3,23 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (40936 / 42301) \times 100 = 96,77 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (19 / 1384) \times 100 = 1,37 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1365 / 1384) \times 100 = 98,63 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (1482 / 42418) \times 100 = 3,49 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (40936 / 42418) \times 100 = 96,51 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (1501 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,43 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (42301 / 43802) \times 100 = 96,57 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (1384 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,16 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (42418 / 43802) \times 100 = 96,84 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,39227524
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,39293390
 Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 60,77 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,38448389
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,59938172

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU)= 0,93413543
 p (IOI)= 0,00267111

Liu et al. did provide evidence of an exclusion relationship between pravastatin and lung cancer ($k = -0,02039443$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000131) with p (EXCL) = 0,99956623 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00043368), while the study design (p (IOI) = 0,00267111) has been unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

US veterans. Chest. 2007 May;131(5):1282-8. doi: 10.1378/chest.06-0931. PMID: 17494779.

¹⁰⁹Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. Oncotarget. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

3.5.7.3.3. Pravastatin and cancer Shepherd et al. ¹¹⁰ randomly assigned 6595 men, 45 to 64 years of age, to receive placebo (N = 3293) or 40 mg pravastatin (N = 3302) each evening over an average follow-up period of about 4.9 years (The West of Scotland Coronary Prevention Study). The incidence of cancer in the **pravastatin** group has been reported as $\left(\frac{116}{3302 \times 5}\right) \times 100000 = 702.6 \text{ events per } 100,000 \text{ per year}$. The 1995 incidence of cancer in Scotland according to the **placebo** group has been $\left(\frac{106}{3293 \times 5}\right) \times 100000 = 643.8 \text{ events per } 100,000 \text{ per year}$.

The estimate Scotland's population on 30 June 2009 has been 5,194,000. ¹¹¹ The number of new cases of cancer in 2009 in Scotland (incidence) have been reported as 29,500. ¹¹² The incidence of new cases of cancer in **Scotland 2009** has been about $\left(\frac{29,500}{5,194,000 \times 1}\right) \times 100000 = 567.96 \text{ per } 100,000 \text{ per year}$.

In contrast to the data of Shepherd et al., an estimated 18 million individuals or more with a history of cancer were alive on January 1, 2022, in the United States. ¹¹³ The U.S. resident population has been estimated by the U.S. Census Bureau in 2022 to be 333,287,557. ¹¹⁴ The 2022 U.S. Cancer prevalence per 100,000 U.S. inhabitants is about $\left(\frac{18,000,000}{333,287,557 \times 1}\right) \times 100000 = 5400.7$. In other words, the 2022 U.S. number of living people who have been diagnosed with cancer (prevalence) is 5.4 % of the United states population. In 2022, 1,918,030 new cancer cases are projected by the American Cancer Society to occur in the United States. ¹¹⁵ Th **2022 U.S. Cancer incidence** has been about $\left(\frac{1,918,030}{333,287,557 \times 1}\right) \times 100000 = 575.5 \text{ per } 100,000 \text{ U.S. inhabitants}$ which is comparable to the cancer incidence of Scotland in the year 2009 of about 567.96 per 100,000 per year.

Thus far and against the background of scientific progress (vaccination against human papillomavirus, therapy of Helicobacter pylori etc.) we may reasonably assume that the incidence of cancer in 1995 will have been higher than the same is today. The same has been reported by Shepherd et al. as being $\left(\frac{106}{3293 \times 5}\right) \times 100000 = 643.8 \text{ events per } 100,000 \text{ per year}$, which is to some extent logical. Let these information run again before our minds eyes and some contradictions become apparent. If pravastatin is of use against cancer, as suggested in part by literature, then the incidence of cancer per 100,000 population may not be greater in the pravastatin group than in the overall population. Unfortunately, this was precisely the case (see table 11). The incidence of cancer in the pravastatin group has been greater than in the whole population. Nonetheless, can such a phenomenon occur simply by chance?

¹¹⁰Shepherd J, Cobbe SM, Ford I, Isles CG, Lorimer AR, MacFarlane PW, McKillop JH, Packard CJ. Prevention of coronary heart disease with pravastatin in men with hypercholesterolemia. West of Scotland Coronary Prevention Study Group. N Engl J Med. 1995 Nov 16;333(20):1301-7. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199511163332001. PMID: 7566020.

¹¹¹Scotland's Population 2009: The Registrar General's Annual Review of Demographic Trends 155th Edition

¹¹²Cancer in Scotland. October 2011. Information Services Division. NHS. National Services Scotland

¹¹³American Cancer Society. Cancer Treatment & Survivorship Facts & Figures 2022-2024. Atlanta: American Cancer Society; 2022.

¹¹⁴2022 National and State Population Estimates Press Kit - U.S. Census Bureau

¹¹⁵Siegel RL, Miller KD, Fuchs HE, Jemal A. Cancer statistics, 2022. CA Cancer J Clin. 2022 Jan;72(1):7-33. doi: 10.3322/caac.21708. Epub 2022 Jan 12. PMID: 35020204.

Table 11. Relationship: pravastatin and cancer (Study of Shepherd et al., 1995).

		Cancer		
		YES	NO	
Pravastatin	YES	116	3186	3302
	NO	106	3187	3293
		222	6373	6595

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = +0,00815251$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,76736660
 p (EXCL) = 0,98241092
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,96486978$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,47747748$

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,76736660
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_1) = 4,07510600
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_1) = 60,61261261
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01743530**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (116 / 6595) \times 100 = 1,76 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (3186 / 6595) \times 100 = 48,31 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (106 / 6595) \times 100 = 1,61 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (3187 / 6595) \times 100 = 48,32 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (116 / 3302) \times 100 = 3,51 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (3186 / 3302) \times 100 = 96,49 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (106 / 3293) \times 100 = 3,22 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (3187 / 3293) \times 100 = 96,78 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (116 / 222) \times 100 = 52,25 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (106 / 222) \times 100 = 47,75 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (3186 / 6373) \times 100 = 49,99 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (3187 / 6373) \times 100 = 50,01 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (3302 / 6595) \times 100 = 50,07 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (3293 / 6595) \times 100 = 49,93 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (222 / 6595) \times 100 = 3,37 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (6373 / 6595) \times 100 = 96,63 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 1,09135687
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,04520905
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = -9,14 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,09468311
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,04362085

STUDY DESIGN.

$p(\text{IOU}) = 0,46565580$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,46702047$

Shepherd et al. did not provide any evidence of an exclusion relationship between pravastatin and cancer ($k = +0,00815251$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,76736660) even if p (EXCL) = 0,982410917 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,01743530) has been slightly impressive. **Note.** Relative risk reduction (RRR) is one way of re-expressing a risk ratio (RR) as a percentage reduction. A risk ratio (RR) = 1,091356868 translates to a relative risk reduction of $\text{RRR} = (1 - \text{RR}) \times 100 = -9,135686776 \%$. Furthermore, the study design ($p(\text{IOI}) = 0,46702047$) has been very unfair (Barukčić, 2019a). Shepherd et al. did not provide any evidence of an exclusion relationship between pravastatin and cancer ($k = -0,00659313$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,33333697) with p (EXCL) = 0,993328279 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00664951) while the study design ($p(\text{IOI}) = 0,48658074$) has been very unfair (Barukčić, 2019a). In this regard, it is worth pointing out that mathematically, a positive causal relationship ($k > 0$) excludes the possibility of a significant exclusion relationship. In other words, these data of Shepherd et al. are self-contradictory and cannot be considered for further considerations.

3.5.7.3.4. Pravastatin and all cause death At least one point of the study of Shepherd et al. is impressive (see table 12) even if the mortality rate within the placebo group in about 5 years with $(c/\text{not}A) \times 100 = (135/3293) \times 100 = 4,10\%$ has been too small.

Table 12. Relationship: Pravastatin and all cause death (Study of Shepherd et al. , 1995).

		All cause death		
		YES	NO	
Pravastatin	YES	106	3196	3302
	NO	135	3158	3293
		241	6354	6595

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,02370085$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,03140654
p (EXCL) = 0,98392722
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,96789824
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,56016598

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,03140654
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 3,40278619
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 46,62240664
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01594430**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (106 / 6595) \times 100 = 1,61 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (3196 / 6595) \times 100 = 48,46 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (135 / 6595) \times 100 = 2,05 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (3158 / 6595) \times 100 = 47,88 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (106 / 3302) \times 100 = 3,21 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (3196 / 3302) \times 100 = 96,79 \%$
 $(c/\text{not} A) \times 100 = (135 / 3293) \times 100 = 4,10 \%$
 $(d/\text{not} A) \times 100 = (3158 / 3293) \times 100 = 95,90 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (106 / 241) \times 100 = 43,98 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (135 / 241) \times 100 = 56,02 \%$
 $(b/\text{not} B) \times 100 = (3196 / 6354) \times 100 = 50,30 \%$
 $(d/\text{not} B) \times 100 = (3158 / 6354) \times 100 = 49,70 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (3302 / 6595) \times 100 = 50,07 \%$
 $(\text{not} A/N) \times 100 = (3293 / 6595) \times 100 = 49,93 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (241 / 6595) \times 100 = 3,65 \%$
 $(\text{not} B/N) \times 100 = (6354 / 6595) \times 100 = 96,35 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,78304507
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,87443848

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,77584944
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,12153077

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,46277483
p(IOI)= 0,46413950

Shepherd et al. did provide evidence of an exclusion relationship between pravastatin and all cause death ($k = -0,02370085$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,03140654) with p (EXCL) = 0,983927218 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,01594430). However, the study design (**p(IOI) = 0,46413950**) has been very unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

3.5.7.3.5. Fluvastatin and lung cancer Liu et al. ¹¹⁶ provided data about the relationship between fluvastatin and lung cancer (see table 13).

Table 13. Relationship: fluvastatin and lung cancer (Study of Liu et al. , 2016).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Fluvastatin	YES	27	1483	1510
	NO	1357	40935	42292
		1384	42418	43802

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,01481616$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00057979
 p (EXCL) = 0,99938359
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,98211921$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,98049133$

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00057979
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 0,48278146
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 0,52673410
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,00061622

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (27 / 43802) \times 100 = 0,06 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (1483 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,39 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1357 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,10 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (40935 / 43802) \times 100 = 93,45 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (27 / 1510) \times 100 = 1,79 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (1483 / 1510) \times 100 = 98,21 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (1357 / 42292) \times 100 = 3,21 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (40935 / 42292) \times 100 = 96,79 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (27 / 1384) \times 100 = 1,95 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1357 / 1384) \times 100 = 98,05 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (1483 / 42418) \times 100 = 3,50 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (40935 / 42418) \times 100 = 96,50 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (1510 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,45 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (42292 / 43802) \times 100 = 96,55 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (1384 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,16 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (42418 / 43802) \times 100 = 96,84 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,55726940
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,55800323
 Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 44,27 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,54920889
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,43409352

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU) = 0,93392996
 p (IOI) = 0,00287658

Liu et al. did provide evidence of an exclusion relationship between fluvastatin and lung cancer ($k = -0,01481616$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00057979) with p (EXCL) = 0,99938359 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00061622), while the study design (p (IOI) = 0,00287658) has been unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

¹¹⁶Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

3.5.7.3.6. Rosuvastatin and lung cancer Liu et al. ¹¹⁷ provided data about the relationship between rosuvastatin and lung cancer (see table 14).

Table 14. Relationship: rosuvastatin and lung cancer (Study of Liu et al. , 2016).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Rosuvastatin	YES	28	2713	2741
	NO	1356	39705	41061
		1384	42418	43802

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,03158118$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,99936076
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,98978475
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,97976879

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 0,28602700
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 0,56647399
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00063904**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (28 / 43802) \times 100 = 0,06 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (2713 / 43802) \times 100 = 6,19 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1356 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,10 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (39705 / 43802) \times 100 = 90,65 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (28 / 2741) \times 100 = 1,02 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (2713 / 2741) \times 100 = 98,98 \%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (1356 / 41061) \times 100 = 3,30 \%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (39705 / 41061) \times 100 = 96,70 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (28 / 1384) \times 100 = 2,02 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1356 / 1384) \times 100 = 97,98 \%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (2713 / 42418) \times 100 = 6,40 \%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (39705 / 42418) \times 100 = 93,60 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (2741 / 43802) \times 100 = 6,26 \%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (41061 / 43802) \times 100 = 93,74 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (1384 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,16 \%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (42418 / 43802) \times 100 = 96,84 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,30932771
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,31631686
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 69,07 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,30219950
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,67669915

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,90582622
p(IOI)= 0,03098032

Liu et al. did provide evidence of an exclusion relationship between rosuvastatin and lung cancer ($k = -0,03158118$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000) with $p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,99936076$ (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00063904), while the study design ($p(\text{IOI}) = 0,03098032$) has been unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

¹¹⁷Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

3.5.7.3.7. Simvastatin and lung cancer Liu et al. ¹¹⁸ provided data about the relationship between simvastatin and lung cancer (see table 15).

Table 15. Relationship: simvastatin and lung cancer (Study of Liu et al. , 2016).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Simvastatin	YES	37	3381	3418
	NO	1347	39037	40384
		1384	42418	43802

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = -0,03454649$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,99915529
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,98917496
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,97326590
P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 0,40052662
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 0,98916185
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00084435**
PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (37 / 43802) \times 100 = 0,08 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (3381 / 43802) \times 100 = 7,72 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1347 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,08 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (39037 / 43802) \times 100 = 89,12 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (37 / 3418) \times 100 = 1,08 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (3381 / 3418) \times 100 = 98,92 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (1347 / 40384) \times 100 = 3,34 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (39037 / 40384) \times 100 = 96,66 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (37 / 1384) \times 100 = 2,67 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1347 / 1384) \times 100 = 97,33 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (3381 / 42418) \times 100 = 7,97 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (39037 / 42418) \times 100 = 92,03 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (3418 / 43802) \times 100 = 7,80 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (40384 / 43802) \times 100 = 92,20 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (1384 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,16 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (42418 / 43802) \times 100 = 96,84 \%$
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,32454237
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,33540586
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 67,55 %
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,31715049
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,65739988
STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,89037030
p(IOI)= 0,04643624

Liu et al. did provide evidence of an exclusion relationship between simvastatin and lung cancer ($k = -0,03454649$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000) with p (EXCL) = 0,99915529 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00084435), while the study design (p (IOI) = 0,04643624) has been unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

¹¹⁸Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

3.5.7.3.8. Lovastatin and lung cancer Liu et al. ¹¹⁹ provided data about the relationship between lovastatin and lung cancer (see table 16).

Table 16. Relationship: lovastatin and lung cancer (Study of Liu et al. , 2016).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Lovastatin	YES	40	2069	2109
	NO	1344	40349	41693
		1384	42418	43802

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,01623957$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00018638
p (EXCL) = 0,99908680
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,98103367
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,97109827

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00018638
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 0,75865339
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 1,15606936
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00091278**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (40 / 43802) \times 100 = 0,09 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (2069 / 43802) \times 100 = 4,72 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1344 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,07 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (40349 / 43802) \times 100 = 92,12 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (40 / 2109) \times 100 = 1,90 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (2069 / 2109) \times 100 = 98,10 \%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (1344 / 41693) \times 100 = 3,22 \%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (40349 / 41693) \times 100 = 96,78 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (40 / 1384) \times 100 = 2,89 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1344 / 1384) \times 100 = 97,11 \%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (2069 / 42418) \times 100 = 4,88 \%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (40349 / 42418) \times 100 = 95,12 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (2109 / 43802) \times 100 = 4,81 \%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (41693 / 43802) \times 100 = 95,19 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (1384 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,16 \%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (42418 / 43802) \times 100 = 96,84 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,58836562
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,59253444
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 41,16 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,58040749
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,39973743

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,92025478
p(IOI) = 0,01655176

Liu et al. did provide evidence of an exclusion relationship between lovastatin and lung cancer ($k = -0,01623957$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00018638) with $p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,9990868$ (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00091278), while the study design (**$p(\text{IOI}) = 0,01655176$**) has been unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

¹¹⁹Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

3.5.7.3.9. Atorvastatin and lung cancer Liu et al. ¹²⁰ provided data about the relationship between atorvastatin and lung cancer (see table 17).

Table 17. Relationship: atorvastatin and lung cancer (Study of Liu et al. , 2016).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
Atorvastatin	YES	81	5403	5484
	NO	1303	37015	38318
		1384	42418	43802

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
 Causal relationship $k = -0,03639080$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 p (EXCL) = 0,99815077
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,98522976$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,94147399$

P VALUES.
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 1,19638950
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 4,74060694
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,00184752

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (81 / 43802) \times 100 = 0,18 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (5403 / 43802) \times 100 = 12,34 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1303 / 43802) \times 100 = 2,97 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (37015 / 43802) \times 100 = 84,51 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (81 / 5484) \times 100 = 1,48 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (5403 / 5484) \times 100 = 98,52 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (1303 / 38318) \times 100 = 3,40 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (37015 / 38318) \times 100 = 96,60 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (81 / 1384) \times 100 = 5,85 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1303 / 1384) \times 100 = 94,15 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (5403 / 42418) \times 100 = 12,74 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (37015 / 42418) \times 100 = 87,26 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (5484 / 43802) \times 100 = 12,52 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (38318 / 43802) \times 100 = 87,48 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (1384 / 43802) \times 100 = 3,16 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (42418 / 43802) \times 100 = 96,84 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
 RR (necessary condition) = 0,43435617
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,45947739
 Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 56,56 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
 Odds ratio (OR) = 0,42587622
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,53253896

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,84320351$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,09360303$

Liu et al. did provide evidence of an exclusion relationship between atorvastatin and lung cancer ($k = -0,03639080$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000) with p (EXCL) = 0,998150769 (P Value (EXCL) = 0,00184752), while the study design ($p(\text{IOI}) = 0,09360303$) has been unfair (Barukčić, 2019a).

¹²⁰Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

3.5.7.3.10. Statins and lung cancer Liu et al. ¹²¹ investigated the efficacy of individual lipophilia statins like simvastatin, lovastatin, atorvastatin, and fluvastatin, and individual hydrophilia statins like pravastatin and rosuvastatin in relation to lung cancer during the follow-up of patients. (see table 18).

Table 18. Ranking of statins

Ranking	Drug	p(EXCL)	P Value	p(IOI)	Type
1	Pravastatin	0.99956623	0.00043368	0.00267111	Hydrophilia statin
2	Fluvastatin	0.99938359	0.00061622	0.00287658	Lipophilia statin
3	Rosuvastatin	0.99936076	0.00063904	0.03098032	Hydrophilia statin
4	Simvastatin	0.99915529	0.00084435	0.04643624	Lipophilia statin
5	Lovastatin	0.9990868	0.00091278	0.01655176	Lipophilia statin
6	Atorvastatin	0.99815077	0.00184752	0.09360303	Lipophilia statin

The data of Liu et al. ¹²² revealed that individual statins are protecting against lung cancer in descending order as follows: Pravastatin > Fluvastatin > Rosuvastatin > Simvastatin > Lovastatin > Atorvastatin. It is of greater interest to note that pravastatin unlike other statins, does not interact with cytochrome P450 family ¹²³ members. Thereby, pravastatin has the potential to reduce important drug interactions. This might have been one of the reasons why Michael J Seckl et al. ¹²⁴ conducted a randomized (1:1), phase III, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial to investigate whether pravastatin 40 mg combined with standard small-cell lung cancer (SCLC) therapy is of any benefit for patients. The median length of time patients were on study drug was 8.6 months (pravastatin) and 7.8 months (placebo). Michael J Seckl et al. found no benefit for pravastatin 40 mg combined with standard SCLC therapy, neither in all patients nor in several subgroups. In this regard, it should be kept in mind that all statin studies have considered the use of statins for years as necessary to show an effect against lung cancer. Therefore, the usual dosage of statins seem to be effective in the **prevention** of lung cancer, but possibly not in its **treatment**. In order to achieve a therapeutic effect by statins in a very short time, it is possible that the dosage of statins would have to be massively increased into the toxic range, approximately *pravastatin 40 mg per day* × 60 month = *pravastatin 400 mg per day* × 6 month. Seckl et al. failed to consider this fundamental aspect at the design phase and later of their study.

¹²¹Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

¹²²Ibid.

¹²³Hirota T, Fujita Y, Ieiri I. An updated review of pharmacokinetic drug interactions and pharmacogenetics of statins. *Expert Opin Drug Metab Toxicol*. 2020 Sep;16(9):809-822. doi: 10.1080/17425255.2020.1801634. Epub 2020 Aug 6. PMID: 32729746.

¹²⁴Seckl MJ, Ottensmeier CH, Cullen M, Schmid P, Ngai Y, Muthukumar D, Thompson J, Harden S, Middleton G, Fife KM, Crosse B, Taylor P, Nash S, Hackshaw A. Multicenter, Phase III, Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled Trial of Pravastatin Added to First-Line Standard Chemotherapy in Small-Cell Lung Cancer (LUNGSTAR). *J Clin Oncol*. 2017 May 10;35(14):1506-1514. doi: 10.1200/JCO.2016.69.7391. Epub 2017 Feb 27. PMID: 28240967; PMCID: PMC5455702.

3.6. Control group study design

As the next step of this investigation, let us consider the following definitions (see table 19). In general, it is

Table 19. Two by two table and sample space 1

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

It is $E(\underline{B}_t) = N \times (1-p(B_t)) = N \times p(\underline{B}_t)$, $E(b_t) = N \times p(b_t)$, $E(d_t) = N \times p(d_t)$ and $p(\underline{B}_t) = p(b_t) + p(d_t)$, while $E(\dots)$ denotes the expectation value, $p(\dots)$ is the (joint) probability and N is the population or sample size.

3.6.1. Theorem. Sample size of a control group

Theorem 2 (Sample size of a control group). *The sample size of a control group, denoted as $E(\underline{B}_t)$, is determined as follows.*

$$E(\underline{B}_t) = \left(\frac{E(a_t)}{(1 - p_{prevalence}(A_t))} \right) \quad (5)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. Therefore, it is equally true that

$$p(b_t) = p(b_t) \quad (6)$$

and that

$$p(b_t) + p(d_t) = p(b_t) + p(d_t) \quad (7)$$

According to our definition above (see table 19), equation 7 simplifies as

$$p(b_t) + p(d_t) = p(\underline{B}_t) \quad (8)$$

Normalising the relationship of equation 8, we obtain

$$\frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)} + \frac{p(d_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)} = \frac{p(\underline{B}_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)} = 1 \quad (9)$$

Rearranging equation 9, it is

$$\frac{p(d_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)} = 1 - \frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)} \quad (10)$$

Rearranging equation 10, it is

$$p(d_t) = p(\underline{B}_t) \times \left(1 - \frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)}\right) \quad (11)$$

Rearranging equation 11, it is

$$p(\underline{B}_t) = \frac{p(d_t)}{\left(1 - \frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)}\right)} \quad (12)$$

Multiplying equation 12 by a sample size or population size N, it is

$$N \times p(\underline{B}_t) = N \times \left(\frac{p(d_t)}{\left(1 - \frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)}\right)}\right) \quad (13)$$

In so far and according to our definitions above, equation 13 becomes

$$E(\underline{B}_t) = \frac{E(d_t)}{\left(1 - \frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)}\right)} \quad (14)$$

In our understanding, the prevalence of the condition A_t , denoted as $p_{\text{prevalence}}(A_t)$, is given as

$$p_{\text{prevalence}}(A_t) = \left(\frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)}\right) = \left(\frac{N \times p(b_t)}{N \times p(\underline{B}_t)}\right) = \left(\frac{E(b_t)}{E(\underline{B}_t)}\right) \quad (15)$$

Equation 14 simplifies. The sample size of the control group, denoted as $E(\underline{B}_t)$, is given as

$$E(\underline{B}_t) = \frac{E(d_t)}{(1 - p_{\text{prevalence}}(A_t))} \quad (16)$$

□

The study design of a study which is going to investigate the necessary condition or the sufficient condition or the necessary and sufficient condition relationship should assure as much as possible the condition ¹²⁵ $E(\underline{a}_t) = E(\underline{d}_t)$ or that $\text{IOU}(A_t, B_t) = 0$. Under these conditions, equation 16 becomes

$$E(\underline{B}_t) = \frac{E(a_t)}{(1 - p_{\text{prevalence}}(A_t))} \quad (17)$$

Should we be interested in the above logic mentioned, the sample size of a ‘placebo group’ or $E(\underline{A}_t)$ becomes (see equation 16)

$$E(\underline{A}_t) = \frac{E(d_t) = E(a_t)}{\left(1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)}\right)} \quad (18)$$

¹²⁵Barukčić, Ilija. (2022). Conditions and study design. *Causation*, 18(1), 5–99.

while the term $\left(\frac{p(c_t)}{p(A_t)}\right)$ can be simplified. Nevertheless, we can take note of the fact that in the case of a necessary condition should apply that $\mathbf{E(a_t)} = \mathbf{E(B_t)}$. Equation 17 changes slightly. Under conditions of a necessary condition relationship, the number of cases $E(B_t)$ determines the number of controls $E(\underline{B}_t)$ as

$$E(\underline{B}_t) = \frac{E(B_t)}{(1 - p_{\text{prevalence}}(A_t))} \quad (19)$$

4. Discussion

This study has certain limitations. Lung cancer is the most commonly diagnosed cancer and more or less the leading cause of cancer-related deaths globally¹²⁶ Numerous risk factors¹²⁷ of lung cancer including lifestyle factors, environmental tobacco smoke, air pollution, exposure to radon, asbestos, human papillomavirus¹²⁸ infection and others have been suggested for the development of lung cancer. In this view, the trial to demonstrate lung cancer as an outcome of CMV infection may turn out to be wrong. However, Balthesen et al.¹²⁹ were able to characterize the lungs as the major organ site of cytomegalovirus latency and recurrence, and found a 10-fold-higher burden of latent CMV viral genome for the lungs compared to the spleen. The CMV genome remained detectable in lung tissue even after it was cleared to an undetectable level in bone marrow and blood. Even if the reason for this affinity of CMV for the lungs is so far unknown, this fact provides an understandable physiological foundation for the theoretical possibility of a causal relationship between CMV and LC. Indeed, the quality of the data of included studies are to be considered with some degree of caution. Nonetheless, this is what we have, and we have to cope with it for a while. Therefore, among one strength of this study is an analysis using relevant data from the included studies by new statistical methods. There is some reason to accept the hypothesis: without CMV infection, no smoking. However, the study design of the studies used to establish this knowledge is not without problems. That's why it is appropriate to differ strictly between real certain knowledge and only a probably given relationship.

At this point, we would like to take the opportunity to express our hope that the Chinese study group around Li et al.¹³⁰ and that the US study group around Vikas Khurana et al.¹³¹ worked properly and that their data published are of good quality. The conclusions reached in this publication are essentially based on the quality of the data used. Assumed that the data used in this study accurately reflect objective reality, then the conclusions drawn here are logically consistent. In contrast to the statement before, if the data used in this publication cannot be confirmed by other study groups, then the relationship between CMV and LC is very shaky. In any case, it makes sense to take a closer look at the relationship between CMV and LC. However, before very expensive and long lasting studies are carried out, it makes sense to check the serum prevalence of CMV (CMV IgG and IgM) and the serum prevalence of other viruses in a pilot study of a LC population and a control population. In order to obtain reliable results, it is necessary to consider the sensitivity and specificity of the laboratory kit

¹²⁶Ferlay J, Colombet M, Soerjomataram I, Mathers C, Parkin DM, Piñeros M, Znaor A, Bray F. Estimating the global cancer incidence and mortality in 2018: GLOBOCAN sources and methods. *Int J Cancer*. 2019 Apr 15;144(8):1941-1953. doi: 10.1002/ijc.31937. Epub 2018 Dec 6. PMID: 30350310.

¹²⁷Cheng ES, Egger S, Hughes S, Weber M, Steinberg J, Rahman B, Worth H, Ruano-Ravina A, Rawstorne P, Yu XQ. Systematic review and meta-analysis of residential radon and lung cancer in never-smokers. *Eur Respir Rev*. 2021 Feb 2;30(159):200230. doi: 10.1183/16000617.0230-2020. PMID: 33536262; PMCID: PMC9488946.

¹²⁸Karnosky J, Dietmaier W, Knuettel H, Freigang V, Koch M, Koll F, Zeman F, Schulz C. HPV and lung cancer: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Cancer Rep (Hoboken)*. 2021 Aug;4(4):e1350. doi: 10.1002/cnr2.1350. Epub 2021 Feb 23. PMID: 33624444; PMCID: PMC8388180.

¹²⁹Balthesen M, Messerle M, Reddehase MJ. Lungs are a major organ site of cytomegalovirus latency and recurrence. *J Virol*. 1993 Sep;67(9):5360-6. doi: 10.1128/JVI.67.9.5360-5366.1993. PMID: 8394453; PMCID: PMC237936.

¹³⁰Li Z, Tang Y, Tang N, Feng Q, Zhong H, Liu YM, Wang LM, He F. High anti-human cytomegalovirus antibody levels are associated with the progression of essential hypertension and target organ damage in Han Chinese population. *PLoS One*. 2017 Aug 24;12(8):e0181440. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0181440. PMID: 28837559; PMCID: PMC5570371.

¹³¹Khurana V, Bejjanki HR, Caldito G, Owens MW. Statins reduce the risk of lung cancer in humans: a large case-control study of US veterans. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1282-8. doi: 10.1378/chest.06-0931. PMID: 17494779.

used and to assure a very good study design.

Assumed we want to investigate 100 LC patients, the control group follows as outlined now. The CMV prevalence in the population is about 70-90% which should be given with the control sample too. We set CMV prevalence as $p(\text{CMV}) = 0.9$. Our goal is to investigate a necessary condition relationship. Therefore, the study design should assure as much as possible that ¹³² $a=d$ or $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$. In this case, $d = 100 = 10\% = (1/10) * N(\text{Control group})$. The size of the control group would have to be about $N(\text{Control group}) = 10 * d = 10 * 100 = 1000$. Under these assumptions, a matching 1:10 could be appropriate enough. Again, let $p(\text{CMV})$ denote the prevalence of CMV within a population expressed as a probability or as relative frequency, then the sample size of the control group (see equation 17) would be given as

$$\text{Sample size (Control group)} = E(B_t) = \frac{E(a_t)}{(1 - p_{\text{prevalence}}(A_t))} = \left(\frac{1}{1 - p(\text{CMV})} \right) \times (E(d_t) = E(a_t)) = \left(\frac{1}{1 - 0.9} \right) \times (100) = 1000 \quad (20)$$

Furthermore, at this point **it may remain an open question whether there is a causal relationship between CMV and LC**. However, a very important result of this work is that we can approach to the answer of this question indirectly and very precisely. Theorem 7 of the publication Single and compound conditions ¹³³, Version 2, known as $((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t)$ is of great practical use and provides us with a reliable logical methodology of advancing from the known to the elusive unknown, provided that we can rely on excellent study or experimental data.

Furthermore, we cannot fail to recognise the increasing published evidence ^{134, 135, 136, 137, 138} that statins or 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme (HMG-CoA) reductase inhibitors after long-term use possess excellent protective effects against lung cancer. This finding is supported by an analysis of the same data by different statistical methods. However, numerous studies ^{139, 140, 141, 142, 143},

¹³²Barukčić, Ilija. (2022). Conditions and study design. *Causation*, 18(1), 5–99.

¹³³Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Single and compound conditions. *Causation*, 18(10), 5–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535107>, p. 24.

¹³⁴Fatehi Hassanabad A, McBride SA. Statins as Potential Therapeutics for Lung Cancer: Molecular Mechanisms and Clinical Outcomes. *Am J Clin Oncol*. 2019 Sep;42(9):732-736. doi: 10.1097/COC.0000000000000579. PMID: 31335352.

¹³⁵Chen Y, Li X, Zhang R, Xia Y, Shao Z, Mei Z. Effects of statin exposure and lung cancer survival: A meta-analysis of observational studies. *Pharmacol Res*. 2019 Mar;141:357-365. doi: 10.1016/j.phrs.2019.01.016. Epub 2019 Jan 11. PMID: 30641276.

¹³⁶Tulbah AS. Inhaled Atorvastatin Nanoparticles for Lung Cancer. *Curr Drug Deliv*. 2022;19(10):1073-1082. doi: 10.2174/1567201819666220426091500. PMID: 35473526.

¹³⁷Marcianò G, Palleria C, Casarella A, Rania V, Basile E, Catarisano L, Vocca C, Bianco L, Pelaia C, Cione E, D'Agostino B, Citraro R, De Sarro G, Gallelli L. Effect of Statins on Lung Cancer Molecular Pathways: A Possible Therapeutic Role. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel)*. 2022 May 10;15(5):589. doi: 10.3390/ph15050589. PMID: 35631415; PMCID: PMC9144184.

¹³⁸Amin F, Fathi F, Reiner Ž, Banach M, Sahebkar A. The role of statins in lung cancer. *Arch Med Sci*. 2021 Mar 18;18(1):141-152. doi: 10.5114/aoms/123225. PMID: 35154535; PMCID: PMC8826694.

¹³⁹Grabarek BO, Boroń D, Morawiec E, Michalski P, Palazzo-Michalska V, Pach Ł, Dziuk B, Świder M, Zmarzły N. Crosstalk between Statins and Cancer Prevention and Therapy: An Update. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel)*. 2021 Nov 25;14(12):1220. doi: 10.3390/ph14121220. PMID: 34959621; PMCID: PMC8704600.

¹⁴⁰Khurana V, Bejjanki HR, Caldito G, Owens MW. Statins reduce the risk of lung cancer in humans: a large case-control study of US veterans. *Chest*. 2007 May;131(5):1282-8. doi: 10.1378/chest.06-0931. PMID: 17494779.

¹⁴¹Ahmadi M, Amiri S, Pecic S, Machaj F, Rosik J, Los MJ, Alizadeh J, Mahdian R, da Silva Rosa SC, Schaafsma D, Shojaei S, Madrakian T, Zeki AA, Ghavami S. Pleiotropic effects of statins: A focus on cancer. *Biochim Biophys Acta Mol Basis Dis*. 2020 Dec 1;1866(12):165968. doi: 10.1016/j.bbadis.2020.165968. Epub 2020 Sep 12. PMID: 32927022.

¹⁴²Nielsen SF, Nordestgaard BG, Bojesen SE. Statin use and reduced cancer-related mortality. *N Engl J Med*. 2013 Feb 7;368(6):576-7. doi: 10.1056/NEJMc1214827. PMID: 23388012.

¹⁴³Matusiewicz L, Meissner J, Toporkiewicz M, Sikorski AF. The effect of statins on cancer cells—review. *Tumour Biol*. 2015 Jul;36(7):4889-904. doi: 10.1007/s13277-015-3551-7. Epub 2015 May 23. PMID: 26002574.

¹⁴⁴, ¹⁴⁵, ¹⁴⁶ provided us at the end with various contradictory results. Thus far, what can be said with certainty at this time is that statins are neither a necessary nor a sufficient condition of cancer. First of all, cancer existed before the existence of statins. Therefore, statins are for sure not a necessary condition of cancer. Secondly, the intake of statins does not lead to cancer with the consequence that statins are not a sufficient condition of cancer. In other words, statins are certainly not a cause or the cause of cancer. In point of fact and logically, statins can only protect humans against cancer or are completely independent of cancer and have nothing to do with cancer. The studies, which have been examined in this publication, proved quite convincingly that a long-term use of statins protect people against lung cancer. As long as we may rely on the data of Liu et al. ¹⁴⁷ the protection against lung cancer by statins is given in descending order as follows:

Pravastatin > Fluvastatin > Rosuvastatin > Simvastatin > Lovastatin > Atorvastatin.

¹⁴⁴Mei Z, Liang M, Li L, Zhang Y, Wang Q, Yang W. Effects of statins on cancer mortality and progression: A systematic review and meta-analysis of 95 cohorts including 1,111,407 individuals. *Int J Cancer*. 2017 Mar 1;140(5):1068-1081. doi: 10.1002/ijc.30526. PMID: 27859151.

¹⁴⁵Lai SW, Liao KF, Lin CL, Sung FC, Cheng YH. Statins use and female lung cancer risk in Taiwan. *Libyan J Med*. 2012 Dec 27;7(1):1-3. doi: 10.3402/ljm.v7i0.20123. PMID: 23272648; PMCID: PMC3532353.

¹⁴⁶Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

¹⁴⁷Liu JC, Yang TY, Hsu YP, Hao WR, Kao PF, Sung LC, Chen CC, Wu SY. Statins dose-dependently exert a chemopreventive effect against lung cancer in COPD patients: a population-based cohort study. *Oncotarget*. 2016 Sep 13;7(37):59618-59629. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.11162. PMID: 27517752; PMCID: PMC5312335.

5. Conclusion

There is some slight evidence that CMV and LC are causally related. Our confidence is running high that the relationship

without CMV infection, no human lung cancer

is true.

Acknowledgments

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

I would like to dedicate this article to Katrin (Hamburg, Germany).

Liebe Katrin, werde bald wieder ganz gesund.

Liebe Grüße,

Helke und Ilija.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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